

Examining the Impact of Micro Social Media Influencers on Consumer Behavior and Brand Engagement

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Abstract

In recent years, the landscape of influencer marketing has shifted significantly towards the use of micro social media influencers, who have a smaller but highly engaged following. This research paper looks into the impact of micro influencers on consumer behaviour and brand engagement in the context of digital marketing. The study uses a comprehensive literature review to examine a theoretical framework that incorporates key concepts such as attitude, purchasing decisions and buying behaviour in order to elucidate the mechanisms by which micro influencers influence consumer decisions and brand interactions. This study aims to explore the extent of this influence by employing a questionnaire-based survey method. A structured questionnaire was developed to collect data from participants. The survey was administered to both consumers and brands, seeking to capture perspectives from diverse stakeholders within the marketing ecosystem. Questions were designed to assess perceptions of micro influencers' authenticity, relatability, and niche expertise, as well as the perceived impact of influencer collaborations on brand visibility, reach, and engagement. The findings highlight the substantial influence wielded by micro influencers over consumer purchasing decisions, buying behaviour, and attitudes.

Key words: Purchasing decisions, Buying behaviour, Attitude, Micro-Influencer, Social media.

Introduction

The evolution of Internet technology, coupled with the rise of social media platforms and the e-commerce market, has led to the emergence of influencer marketing as a significant phenomenon. This trend has been further accelerated by the circumstances precipitated by the COVID-19 pandemic, during which individuals spent considerable time at home due to social restrictions and lockdown measures. Influencer marketing and social media are closely intertwined, as influencers rely on social media platforms for exposure to gain fame, while these platforms depend on influencers to maintain their appeal to the public. Popular social media platforms for influencer marketing include Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, and Snapchat. According to (Haenlein et al., 2020), influencers encompass individuals who have attained notable fame as athletes, musicians, actors, or accomplished individuals in specific fields. Additionally, influencers may also include those who have gained prominence within the platform itself through exceptional content and heightened engagement with their audience.

With the rise of social media as a prominent advertising platform, brands increasingly collaborate with influencers. Influencers are categorized based on their follower count, with micro-influencers typically having fewer than 100K followers and macro-influencers boasting millions. While micro-influencers lack a large following and substantial brand equity, they are perceived as more trustworthy and relatable, often engaging more with their audience compared to celebrities or mega-influencers (Williams, 2019). However, existing research often overlooks these distinctions and the mechanisms through which influencers influence their audience (Liu et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2019; Xue et al., 2020). Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap by exploring how micro-influencers affect followers' purchase intentions through the lens of parasocial interaction. Parasocial interaction refers to a psychological bond where

followers view media personalities as friends despite limited direct interaction (Gleich, 1997; Rihl & Wegener, 2019). We propose that micro-influencer credibility and transparency enhance parasocial interaction, ultimately leading to increased purchase intentions among followers.

Significance of the study

This study holds notable importance as it delves into the dynamic realm of influencer marketing, focusing specifically on the growing significance of micro social media influencers. With brands increasingly channelling their resources into digital marketing initiatives, it becomes imperative to grasp the implications of micro influencers on consumer behavior and brand interaction. By comprehending how these influencers wield influence in the digital sphere, brands can better strategize their marketing campaigns to ensure optimal reach and engagement. Thus, this research serves as a valuable resource for guiding decision-making processes in the planning and execution of digital marketing strategies.

Scope of the study

The study focuses on investigating how micro influencers affect consumer decisions and interactions with brands. It aims to explore the various ways in which these influencers influence consumer behavior, such as shaping attitudes, impacting purchasing decisions, and influencing overall buying behavior. By thoroughly analyzing these key concepts, the research aims to offer a deep and thorough understanding of the specific role micro influencers play within the digital marketing landscape.

Objectives of the study

To examine the degree of influence micro influencers, have on consumer perceptions and behaviors
To evaluate how consumers perceive the authenticity, relatability, and expertise of micro influencers.
To investigate how influencer collaborations affect brand visibility, reach, and engagement

Review of Literature

Jason Weismueller, 2023

The impact of video characteristics within influencer marketing campaigns on consumer engagement, focusing on liking and commenting behaviors. It identifies a positive correlation between emotionality in post descriptions and consumer engagement, underscoring the rising effectiveness of video content in captivating consumers compared to text-based content. Despite this trend, there exists a research gap concerning the specific attributes of influencer posts that drive engagement, particularly within video content. This review aims to fill this void by examining the influence of emotional facial expressions in videos and corresponding post descriptions on consumer engagement. Drawing upon a sample of 2,376 social media posts from Instagram, the study employs video analysis tools and text-analytics software to analyze the relationship between video characteristics, emotional content, and consumer engagement metrics. Surprisingly, the findings reveal a negative association between emotional facial expressions in videos and consumer engagement, while emphasizing the positive impact of emotional post descriptions on engagement levels. Furthermore, the study highlights a notable moderation effect of product category on the relationship between emotionality in post descriptions and consumer engagement. This review underscores the importance of understanding the complex interplay between video attributes, emotional content, and consumer engagement in influencer marketing, paving the way for future research endeavors to enhance our comprehension of effective strategies in this domain. (Jason Weismueller, 2023)

Ligita Zailskaitė 2021

The influence of marketing communication (MC) within social media (SM) on brand equity (BE), with a focus on the mediating role of consumer engagement behavior (CEB) in shaping BE. The study categorizes CEB into three levels: consuming, contributing, and creating, and investigates their interplay

with functional and hedonic content generated on SM platforms. Through a survey-based empirical study involving 401 respondents in Lithuania, the research explores the mediation effects of CEB on the relationship between MC and BE, revealing new mediation pathways and confirming the model's robustness through control variables. The findings highlight the significant role of CEB via SM platforms in mediating the impact of MC on BE, emphasizing the importance of companies in developing utilitarian content to foster consumer engagement and enhance brand loyalty over the long term. (Ligita Zailskaitė-Jakstė, 2021)

Anchal Dhingra, 2023

The transformative impact of social media on consumer behavior and preferences, reshaping how individuals interact and make purchasing decisions. Across global platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube, social media has become an integral aspect of daily life, profoundly influencing consumer-brand interactions and decision-making processes. The pervasive influence of social media has led marketers to recognize it as a pivotal tool for targeting audiences effectively. By offering heightened exposure to products and services, social media leverages social proof and personalization, thereby shaping consumer preferences and choices. Moreover, the rise of influencer marketing underscores social media's role in brand promotion, prompting firms to understand and harness its influence on consumer behavior and preferences. Through secondary research, this study underscores the imperative for firms to grasp the expansive reach and impact of social media, urging the development of adept social media marketing strategies to thrive in the contemporary digital landscape. Leveraging social media's potency enables firms to amplify visibility, engage with consumers, and steer consumer behavior and preferences towards desired outcomes. (Dhingra, 2023)

Pawan Kumar, 2023

The influence of social media influencers on consumer engagement and its ramifications within the emerging landscape of the Metaverse. The authors explore the role of social media influencers in shaping customer engagement and discern a significant impact on consumers' perceptions of brand value, satisfaction, and favorability. Through primary research involving a survey of 1013 consumers, predominantly comprising young and educated individuals who follow multiple social media influencers, the study unveils the profound influence wielded by these influencers on consumers' perceptions of brands. The findings underscore the substantial sway of social media influencers in shaping consumer attitudes and behaviors towards brands, emphasizing the importance of understanding and leveraging their influence within the evolving Metaverse environment. (Pawan Kumar, 2023)

Shiromani Gupta, 2022

In this paper, the authors provided a model for brand communication from social media influencers (SMIs) that evaluates the effect of source and content characteristics in the formation of consumers' cognitive, emotional, and behavioural engagement with the endorsed brand. a model for brand communication facilitated by social media influencers (SMIs), examining the influence of source and content characteristics on consumers' cognitive, emotional, and behavioral engagement with the endorsed brand. Through survey responses from 316 Instagram users selected via systematic random sampling, the study employs structural equation modeling to analyze the data. The findings underscore the significant positive impact of SMIs' credibility and similarities between SMIs and consumers on all dimensions of consumer brand engagement (CBE). Moreover, the study delineates how the informativeness of SMI content predominantly affects cognitive and behavioral aspects of engagement, while content entertainment primarily enhances emotional engagement. These insights offer valuable guidance to marketing practitioners in selecting appropriate SMIs and designing content to achieve specific or multiple CBE objectives. (Shiromani Gupta, 2022)

Bruno Godey, 2016

The impact of social media marketing efforts on brand equity and consumer behavior within the luxury sector, focusing on pioneering brands such as Burberry, Dior, Gucci, Hermes, and Louis Vuitton. Through

a survey of 845 luxury brand consumers across Chinese, French, Indian, and Italian markets, the study employs a structural equation model to explore the relationship between social media marketing efforts and key outcomes such as brand preference, price premium, and loyalty. The research identifies five dimensions of social media marketing efforts (entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and word of mouth) and demonstrates their significant positive effects on brand equity, particularly on brand awareness and brand image. By addressing gaps in prior literature, this study provides valuable insights into the mechanisms through which social media marketing contributes to the success of luxury brands, offering implications for marketing strategies in the luxury sector. (Bruno Godey, 2016)

S. Hudson, 2016

The impact of social media interactions on consumer-brand relationships, emphasizing the positive influence of social media use, particularly when consumers anthropomorphize the brand and seek to minimize uncertainty. Despite the increasing allocation of marketing resources to social media programs by companies, there remains a dearth of research exploring the association between social media use and consumer-brand relationships. To address this gap, three studies were conducted, spanning France, the U.K., and the U.S., to investigate individual and national differences in the relationship between social media use and customer brand relationships. The findings reveal that social media engagement correlates positively with brand relationship quality, with a stronger effect observed among individuals exhibiting high levels of anthropomorphism towards brands. Subsequent experiments validate these findings and highlight the moderating role of cultural differences, particularly in uncertainty avoidance. The study presents robust and convergent evidence across diverse consumer samples and product categories, indicating that engaging customers via social media fosters stronger consumer-brand relationships and enhances word-of-mouth communication, particularly among consumers who anthropomorphize brands and exhibit lower uncertainty avoidance tendencies. (S. Hudson, 2016)

Shen Zheng 2021

Irish fashion micro-influencers, particularly market mavens, have the highest impact on consumer engagement on social media, with occasion-related microblogs increasing engagement. This study aims to find how can fashion micro-influencers and their electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) messages increase consumer engagement on social media, focusing on micro-influencers' influence, typology, eWOM content and consumer engagement. Design/methodology/approach – A total of 20,000 microblogs were collected from Irish fashion micro influencers and analyzed through keyword classification and content analysis in NVivo. The determinants of eWOM persuasiveness for consumer engagement on social media were investigated based on Sussman and Siegal's information adoption model. Findings – The study finds that among the four types of micro-influencers, market mavens and their eWOM messages have the highest impact on consumer engagement on social media, and it presents a repetitive and persuasive eWOM model of market mavens to increase consumer participation. Also, the study discovers that micro-influencers' occasion-related microblogs have an increasing impact on consumer interactions whereas microblogs with brands have a decreasing engagement with consumers on social media. Originality/value – This study advances prior studies on the relationship between influencers' eWOM messages and consumer participation on social media by the development of a persuasive eWOM model of micro-influencers to increase consumer engagement and fill in the lack of relevant literature. Also, findings provide actionable insights for marketing communication practitioners to persuade consumers to participate in eWOM communications and establish strong consumer-brand relationships on social media. (Shen, A persuasive eWOM model for increasing consumer engagement on social media: evidence from on social media: evidence from, 2021)

Lijuan Bai, 2020

The influence of firm-generated content on social media platforms on firm performance and consumer engagement in the context of China. Recognizing the growing importance of social media as a key marketing channel for firms, particularly in China, the study seeks to address the limited understanding of the marketing effectiveness of different types of content. Drawing on dynamic capability theory, the

authors examine the relationship between social media marketing, operationalized by firm-generated content, and its impact on firm performance and consumer engagement. Utilizing data from Sina Microblog, a prominent social media platform in China, the study employs a panel simultaneous equation model to validate these relationships. The findings reveal that firm social media marketing significantly enhances firm performance, with informative and persuasive content exerting both direct and indirect effects on firm performance by influencing consumer engagement. These findings offer valuable insights for both academic research and practical implications for firms seeking to optimize their social media marketing strategies. (Lijuan Bai, 2020)

Rohit Zade

The profound influence of social media on consumer buying behavior, emphasizing its pivotal role in shaping decision-making processes and offering strategic insights for businesses. With the burgeoning population of approximately 4 billion social media users and 5.19 billion mobile phone users globally, understanding the impact of social media on consumer behavior is paramount. The study scrutinizes the interconnectedness between social media and purchasing decisions, highlighting how digital connectivity and mobility have revolutionized brand marketing and consumer choices. Social media emerges as a crucial tool for marketers, providing innovative avenues to engage with consumers effectively. Employing primarily quantitative methods, including online surveys, the study unveils the significant role of social media in guiding consumer purchasing behaviors, particularly in information-seeking and decision-making processes. Consumers readily leverage social media's accessibility to vast information and demonstrate receptivity to targeted advertisements, while social media influencers wield considerable influence across generations. Key elements such as active social media engagement, reliable customer service, and seamless information dissemination emerge as critical factors for fostering consumer trust. As technological advancements continue, the impact of social media on purchasing decisions is anticipated to intensify, necessitating businesses to adapt their marketing strategies accordingly. The impetus for this research stems from the retail industry's challenges in navigating social media marketing strategies and enhancing customer engagement. (Zade)

Bruno Schivinski, 2014

The impact of social media communication on consumer perceptions of brands, focusing on the distinction between user-generated and firm-created content. While user-generated social media communication positively influences brand equity and attitude, firm-created communication predominantly affects brand attitude. Both factors, in turn, positively influence purchase intention across various industries. The study conducted a survey of 504 Facebook users in Poland, analyzing 60 brands across non-alcoholic beverages, clothing, and mobile network operators. Utilizing structural equation modeling, the research elucidates the interplay between user-generated and firm-created social media communication and investigates industry-specific differences. The findings underscore the significant role of user-generated content in shaping consumer perceptions, highlighting its impact on brand equity and attitude, whereas firm-created content primarily influences brand attitude. Moreover, the study reveals the positive influence of brand equity and attitude on purchase intention across industries, with measurement invariance observed across sectors but structural path differences detected. These insights offer valuable implications for researchers and brand managers seeking to understand the dynamics of social media communication and its effects on consumer perceptions of brands. (Bruno Schivinski, 2014)

Methodology

Sources of Data

Primary data: It is first-hand information. The fresh sources from which the researcher gathers the data directly which have not been collected before. Under the primary method the data will be collected with the help of Questionnaires.

Secondary data: Refers to the data which already exists. Under the secondary method the data will be collected from research articles, sample data, internet etc.

Sample Design

To study the perceptions and behaviors of Boomers to Gen z in consuming the social media content which is leading to the change in consumer behaviour and to evaluate the authenticity and relatability of micro influencers which effects the brand engagement

Sample size

The random sample size of 101 Boomers to Gen z aged between 18 – 40 years of either gender were recruited in the study.

Findings and Analysis

Gender
101 responses

Fig 1

Age
101 responses

Fig 2

Analysis: it is evident from the fig .1 that 51.5% percent of the respondents were female.However, balance 47.5% percent were male. It is clear from the above fig .2 that 78.2% percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 18-25 years & 16.8 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 26-30 years.

Have you ever made a purchase based on a recommendation from a micro influencer?
101 responses

Fig 3

Analysis: It is evident from the fig .3, that 41.6% of respondents said "No", they have not made a purchase based on a micro-influencer recommendation.39.6% of respondents said "Yes", they have made a purchase based on a micro-influencer recommendation. 18.8% of respondents said "Maybe", they are unsure about whether they have made a purchase based on a micro-influencer recommendation.

However, the results of this survey do suggest that a significant proportion of people (41.6%) have not made a purchase based on a recommendation from a micro-influencer. This suggests that micro-influencers may not be a valuable tool for marketers looking to reach new customers.

Fig 4

How likely are you to trust a product or service recommended by a micro influencer compared to traditional advertising methods (e.g., TV commercials, print ads)?

101 responses

Fig 5

Analysis: it is evident from the fig .5, Majority are more likely to trust micro-influencers: Combining the "Much more likely" 5.0% and "More likely" 19.8% reveals that a total of 24.8 % of participants are more likely to trust a product or service recommended by a micro-influencer compared to traditional advertising methods. This suggests that micro-influencers have gained significant trust and credibility among consumers.

Significant portion remains neutral: The "Neither likely nor unlikely" 46.5% indicates that a considerable portion of participants remain indifferent to the source of the recommendation, potentially seeking more information or relying on other factors before making a purchase decision.

The combined value of the "Less likely" 19.8% and "Much less likely" 3.0% suggests that a smaller portion of participants still hold more trust in traditional advertising methods compared to micro-influencers.

Have you ever engaged with a brand's social media content after seeing it promoted by a micro influencer?

101 responses

Fig 6

Analysis: it is evident from the fig .6 67.3% of respondents said "Yes", they have ever engaged with a brand's social media content after seeing it promoted by a micro-influencer. This suggests that micro-influencers can be an effective way for brands to reach and engage with consumers.

32.7% of respondents said "No", they have never engaged with a brand's social media content after seeing it promoted by a micro-influencer. This suggests that not all micro-influencer marketing is successful, and it is important for brands to carefully select influencers who are a good fit for their target audience.

Overall, how influential do you believe micro influencers are in shaping consumer purchasing decisions?

101 responses

Fig 7

Analysis: it is evident from the fig .7, The combined value of the "Extremely influential" (2.0%) and "Very influential" (20.8%), Majority perceive micro-influencers as moderately influential. This indicates

that a significant portion of participants perceive micro-influencers to have a high level of influence on consumer purchasing decisions. This suggests that micro-influencers can be a powerful marketing tool for brands. Majority perceive micro-influencers as moderately influential.

Gradual decrease in influence perception: The pie chart demonstrates a gradual decrease in the percentage of respondents as we move from the "Extremely influential" towards the "Not influential at all". This suggests that while a majority view micro-influencers positively, a portion of the population remains unconvinced about their influence.

Would you recommend products promoted by micro-influencers to friends or family?

101 responses

Fig 8

Analysis: it is evident from the fig .8, Slight majority willing to recommend: A slight majority of respondents (22.8%) indicated that they would recommend products promoted by micro-influencers to friends or family. This suggests that micro-influencers can be a somewhat effective marketing tool for brands, as their recommendations can influence the purchasing decisions of others.

Significant undecided group: A majority of respondents (56.4%) were unsure about whether they would recommend products promoted by micro-influencers. This highlights the need for micro-influencers to build trust and credibility with their audience to ensure their recommendations are effective.

Relatively small group unwilling to recommend: A relatively small group of respondents (20.8%) said they would not recommend products promoted by micro-influencers. This suggests that while micro-influencers can be effective, they may not be suitable for all brands or products.

Do you believe micro-influencer collaborations improve brand engagement with consumers?

101 responses

Fig 9

Analysis: It is evident from the fig .9, A significant portion of respondents 54.5% believe that micro-influencer collaborations can improve brand engagement with consumers. This suggests that micro-influencers may be a valuable tool for brands looking to increase brand awareness and connect with their target audience.

slightly significant portion of respondents 34.7% were unsure about the effectiveness of micro-influencers. This suggests that more research is needed to understand the factors that contribute to the success of micro-influencer marketing campaigns.

A relatively small group of respondents 10.9% do not believe that micro-influencers are effective in improving brand engagement. This highlights the need for brands to carefully consider their target audience and the specific micro-influencers they partner with to ensure successful campaigns.

How does micro-influencer collaboration affect your perception of brand authenticity?

101 responses

Fig 10

Analysis: It is evident from the fig 10, Nearly half perceive increased authenticity: Almost half of the respondents (46%) believe that micro-influencer collaboration increases their perception of brand authenticity. This suggests that micro-influencers can be a valuable tool for brands to build trust and credibility with consumers.

A significant portion of respondents (48.5%) believe that micro-influencer collaboration has no effect on their perception of brand authenticity. This suggests that micro-influencer marketing needs to be carefully executed to ensure it resonates with the target audience and avoids inauthentic partnerships.

Small minority perceives decreased authenticity: A small minority of respondents (7.5%) believe that micro-influencer collaboration decreases their perception of brand authenticity. This could be due to concerns about inauthentic influencer endorsements or a general skepticism towards influencer marketing.

How influential are micro-influencer collaborations in your purchase decisions compared to other forms of advertising?

101 responses

Fig 11

Analysis: It is evident from the fig 11, Smaller group finds them influential, A smaller portion of respondents (7.9% + 23.8% + 51.5% = 83.2%) find micro-influencer collaborations to be influential (very influential or influential or somewhat influential) in their purchase decisions compared to other forms of advertising. This suggests that micro-influencers can be a powerful tool for brands to reach and influence consumers.

Small minority finds micro-influencers somewhat influential or not influential, the majority of respondents (4.9% + 12.9% = 17.8%) find micro-influencers not very influential, or not influential at all in their purchase decisions. This highlights the need for brands to carefully consider their target audience and the specific micro-influencers they partner with to ensure successful campaigns.

Do you believe micro-influencer collaborations enhance the visibility of brands/products?

101 responses

Fig 12

Analysis: It is evident from the fig 12, Nearly half of the respondents (46.5%) believe that micro-influencer marketing makes products more appealing, suggesting that micro-influencers can be a persuasive marketing tool. micro-influencer collaborations enhance the visibility of brands.

Significant portion of respondents (37.6%) is unsure about the impact of micro-influencer collaborations enhance the visibility of brands. 1.0% believe that that the micro-influencer collaborations do not enhance the visibility of brands.

How likely are you to engage with a brand/product after seeing it promoted by a micro-influencer?

101 responses

Fig 13

Analysis: It is evident from the fig 13, (6%+35.6%=41%) are very likely and likely to engage with a brand or product after seeing it promoted by a micro-influencer. This suggests that micro-influencers can be an effective way for brands to reach and engage with consumers.

Significant portion is neutral: A significant portion of respondents (50.5%) are unsure about whether they would engage with a brand or product after seeing it promoted by a micro-influencer. This highlights the need for micro-influencers to build trust and credibility with their audience to ensure their recommendations are effective.

Smaller group is unlikely to engage: A smaller group of respondents (3%+5%=8%) are unlikely to engage with a brand or product after seeing it promoted by a micro-influencer. This could be due to a general skepticism of influencer marketing, a lack of trust in the specific micro-influencer, or a negative perception of the product category being advertised.

Conclusion

The analysis of the presented data highlights the substantial influence wielded by micro-influencer marketing on consumer behavior and attitudes. It becomes evident that micro-influencers hold considerable sway over purchasing decisions, as evidenced by the considerable number of respondents who reported making purchases based on their endorsements. The emphasis on trustworthiness underscores the necessity for authentic partnerships between brands and influencers, emphasizing the pivotal role of credibility in driving consumer trust. Despite some reservations expressed by respondents, micro-influencers are generally perceived as influential, particularly within younger demographics, indicating their potential as effective marketing assets. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of micro-influencer campaigns appears to vary, given the diverse perspectives on their impact on brand engagement and authenticity. In essence, while micro-influencers present a promising avenue for brands to connect with consumers, strategic selection and alignment with target demographics are imperative to capitalize fully on the opportunities afforded by micro-influencer marketing.

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